

Oxidative decarboxylation and deamination of essential amino acids by *N*-Bromonicotinamide – A kinetic study

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of valine, leucine, isoleucine and phenylalanine by *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN) in acetic acid-water in presence of hydrochloric acid has been studied. The reaction shows inverse order dependence on oxidant and $[H^+]$. Increase in [amino acid] has a slight positive effect on the rate, indicating fractional order dependence. Addition of salts like K_2SO_4 , Na_2SO_4 , KCl to the reaction medium has no effect on the rate. Increase in temperature increases the rate of the reaction. The activation parameters have been computed. A mechanism consistent with the results has been proposed.

Keywords : Kinetics, oxidation, valine, leucine, isoleucine, phenylalanine, *N*-bromonicotinamide, mechanism.

Introduction

Amino acids serve important functions in biological systems and play a significant role in metabolism. They are also employed in biochemical, microbiological and nutrition investigations. Some of them are employed as dietary supplements. Amino acids represent for organism forerunners of essential biomolecules such as proteins, hormones, enzymes etc. Also, they may serve as energy source, losing their amino group by two pathways : transamination and oxidative deamination. The steps of oxidative deaminations are shown in the following Scheme 1¹.

Scheme 1. Oxidative deamination of amino acids.

The degradative metabolism of glutamic acid in animals involves oxidative deamination or transamination followed by oxidation of the resulting α -keto glutarate in the citric acid cycle².

Synthetic methodology, as the building block of organic synthesis, continuously seeks for new reagents, better reaction conditions, and more efficient and selective methods. In this regard, a large group of compounds entitled *N*-halo reagents are widely used in fine organic synthesis. These include *N*-halo derivatives of amines, amides,

imides, urea, saccharins, sulfonamides, sulfonimides etc. Some specific features of *N*-halo reagents such as high activity of the *N*-X bond and various modes of its splitting, determine their wide application in organic synthesis. Depending on the conditions, a number of highly reactive intermediates can be formed including halogen radicals, halogen cations, halogen anions, *N*-radicals, *N*-cations, *N*-anions, etc. Consequently, *N*-halo reagents have the potential to promote important reactions such as halogenation, oxidation and protection as well as formation of C-X, C-O and C=O bonds. In addition to the numer-

ous organic and inorganic halogenating agents, *N*-halo reagents play an especially important role in the chemistry of natural compounds³.

Banerji and co-workers have studied the oxidation of neutral and acidic α -amino acids by TBATB (tetrabutylammonium tribromide) in aqueous acetic acid solution, and the mechanistic aspects are discussed⁴. Kushwaha⁵ and co-workers investigated the complexation of copper(II) with model dipeptides of tyrosine and phenylalanine over a wide range of pH. Sivasankaran Nair and co-workers

studied the Schiff base complexes of some metal ions with vanillin and amino acids⁶. Kinetics of oxidation of Ser, Pro, Leu, Trp, Thr, Phe, Met, His by sodium salts of 2-*p*-phenylsulphonic acid-2-phenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl and 2,2'-*d*-*p*-phenylsulphonic acid-2-phenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl at isoelectric point of amino acids has been studied by Gabriela Ionita¹ and co-workers. Hiran and co-workers carried out oxidation of Gly, Ala, Val, iso-Leu, nor-Leu and Phe by pyridinium bromochromate in an aquo-acetic acid medium⁷.

This paper describes a detailed investigation of the kinetics of oxidation of valine, leucine, isoleucine and phenylalanine by a newly developed oxidant *N*-Bromonicotinamide (NBN)⁸⁻¹⁰ in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of hydrochloric acid. It is a mild, efficient, stable and less expensive oxidant. It possesses antimicrobial activity against *E. coli*, *Solmonella enterocolitica*, *Shigella flexneri* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity as well. It is found to have pharmacological activity in general, CNS (central nervous system) stimulant activity in particular. Its chlorine analog has been extensively studied by Vivekanandan¹¹⁻¹³ and co-workers.

Results and discussion

The kinetic results for the decarboxylation of valine, leucine, isoleucine and phenylalanine, by *N*-bromonicotinamide (NBN) can be summarized as follows. As the results are similar, only representative data are given. The kinetic studies were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions with [amino acid] \gg [NBN].

Effect of varying [oxidant] :

The oxidation was carried out with different initial concentrations of NBN. The pseudo-first order rate constants decrease with increase in the initial concentration of the oxidant. But in each kinetic run, the reaction shows no deviation whatsoever from the first order plot (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of variation of [NBN] on reaction rate

[Sub] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³,
[NaClO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, H₂O : CH₃COOH (1 : 1),
Hg(CH₃COO)₂ = 0.005 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 308 K

[NBN] 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_{\text{obs}} 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	Val	Leu	Ile	Phe
4.0	10.23	10.35	11.15	11.63
5.0	9.92	10.04	10.84	11.32
6.0	9.70	9.82	10.62	11.10
7.0	9.53	9.65	10.45	10.93
8.0	9.43	9.55	10.35	10.83

Effect of varying [amino acid] :

At constant [H⁺], with the [amino acid] in excess, the plot of log ($E_t - E_\infty$) (where E_t is the E.M.F. of the cell at time t and E_∞ , the corresponding value at the completion of the reaction) vs time is linear, indicating a first order dependence of rate on [NBN]. Increase in [amino acid] has a slight positive effect on the rate, indicating fractional order dependence of rate on [amino acid]¹⁴ (Table 2).

Table 2. Effect of variation of [Sub] on reaction rate

[NBN] = 0.004 mol dm⁻³, [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³,
[NaClO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, H₂O : CH₃COOH (1 : 1),
Hg(CH₃COO)₂ = 0.005 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 308 K

[Sub] 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_{\text{obs}} 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	Val	Leu	Ile	Phe
4.0	10.23	10.35	11.15	11.63
5.0	10.49	10.61	11.41	11.89
6.0	10.68	10.80	11.60	12.08
7.0	10.80	10.92	11.72	12.20
8.0	11.08	11.20	12.00	12.48

Effect of varying [H⁺] :

The rates decreased with increase in [H⁺], at fixed [NBN] and [amino acid], showing inverse order dependence in [H⁺] (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of variation of [HCl]

[Sub] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³, [NBN] = 0.004 mol dm⁻³,
[NaClO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, H₂O : CH₃COOH (1 : 1),
Hg(CH₃COO)₂ = 0.005 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 308 K

[HCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	$k_{\text{obs}} 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$			
	Val	Leu	Ile	Phe
0.8	10.23	10.35	11.15	11.63
0.9	9.12	9.16	9.71	11.02
1.0	8.09	8.19	8.14	10.35
1.1	7.17	7.08	6.54	9.87

Effect of variation of dielectric constant of the medium (Table 4) :

An increase in the rate constant is noticed on decreasing the dielectric constant of the medium. Plot of log k_{obs} vs $1/D$ ($r = 0.9901$) where D is the dielectric constant of the medium, gives straight line with positive slope¹⁵. The reaction rate increased with an increase in the percentage of acetic acid, suggesting that a low dielectric medium favors the oxidation⁷. Amis has shown that a plot of log k_{obs} vs $1/D$ gives a straight line, with a positive slope for a reaction between a cation and a dipole. This concept

Table 4. Effect of variation of [CH₃COOH : H₂O] on reaction rate

[Sub] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³, [NBN] = 0.004 mol dm⁻³,
 [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, [NaClO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³,
 Hg(CH₃COO)₂ = 0.005 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 308 K

CH ₃ COOH (%)	H ₂ O (%)	D	<i>k</i> _{obs} 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)			
			Val	Leu	Ile	Phe
50	50	37.50	10.23	10.35	11.15	11.63
55	55	34.75	11.93	11.64	12.85	13.33
60	40	31.50	13.89	13.89	14.81	15.29
65	35	28.50	16.13	16.25	17.05	17.53

agrees with the present observations, where a positive ion and a dipole are involved in the rate limiting step of Scheme 2¹⁶.

Effect of addition of nicotinamide :

The rate of reaction decreases on adding nicotinamide (NA). Thus added nicotinamide has a retarding effect on the rate of oxidation. Further the plot of 1/*k*_{obs} vs [NA] is linear indicating inverse dependence of rate on [NA]¹⁷.

Effect of added salts on reaction rate :

The effect of added salts like Na₂SO₄, KCl, BaCl₂ and K₂SO₄ on the reaction rate was studied by adding various concentrations of these salts, keeping the concentrations of glycine, HCl, NBN constant. It was observed that the rates of oxidation were not altered by the addition of these neutral salts.

Test for free radicals :

The possibility of free radical intervention in the reaction was tested as follows :

The reaction mixture containing acrylonitrile scavenger was kept for 24 h in an inert atmosphere and then diluted. On dilution, formation of precipitate was not observed indicating the absence of free radical intervention in the reaction. Increase in temperature increases the rate of oxidation and plot of log *k*_{obs} vs reciprocal of temperature is linear. The oxidation of neutral amino acids was studied at different temperatures (308 to 328 K) and the activation parameters were evaluated (Table 5).

Mechanism :

The possible oxidizing species in acidified aqueous acetic acid solution are NBN, NBNH⁺, NBNBr, Br₂, HOBr, H₂OBr⁺¹⁸. The observed first order dependence of the reaction rate on NBN rules out NBNBr and molecular bromine as the reactive oxidizing species. NBNH⁺ and H₂OBr may be discarded because of inverse dependence of reaction rate on [H⁺]¹⁹. The same observation has been made in the oxidation of acidic amino acids by

Table 5. Effect of temperature on reaction rate

[Sub] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³, [NBN] = 0.004 mol dm⁻³,
 [HCl] = 0.8 mol dm⁻³, [NaClO₄] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³,
 H₂O : CH₃COOH (1 : 1), Hg(CH₃COO)₂ = 0.005 mol dm⁻³

Temp. (K)	<i>k</i> _{obs} 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)			
	Val	Leu	Ile	Phe
308	10.23	10.35	11.15	11.63
313	12.24	12.36	13.16	13.64
318	14.60	14.72	15.52	16.00
323	17.37	17.49	18.29	18.77
328	20.63	20.75	21.55	22.03

Activation parameters

Substrate	<i>E</i> _a	Δ <i>H</i> [#]	Δ <i>S</i> [#]	Δ <i>G</i> [#]
	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
Val	15.34	12.78	-177.60	67.48
Leu	15.07	12.51	-178.40	67.46
Ile	14.13	11.57	-181.20	67.38
Phe	14.18	11.62	-180.90	67.34

hypobromous acid (Table 1). Of the remaining two, HOBr and not NBN should be the oxidizing species since the rate is also inverse function of nicotinamide concentration. A plot of inverse of the observed rate constant against the nicotinamide concentration is linear (*r* = 0.9920).

The retardation of the rate of oxidation with added nicotinamide suggests that the pre-equilibrium step involves a process in which nicotinamide is one of the products [eq. (2)]. Another possible reaction, disproportionation of NBN to *N,N*-dibromonicotinamide, can be ruled out in view of the strict first order dependence of the reaction rate on NBN. Thus the most likely oxidizing species is HOBr¹⁷.

In acid medium, amino acid exists in its protonated form (SH⁺) which is resistant to attack by NBN. It is observed that the rate has inverse dependence on [H⁺]. Thus the only species possibly controlling the rate of oxidation seems to be RCH(NH₂)COOH.

It is a well known fact that in acid medium amino acids exist in a mixture of zwitter-ionic and cationic form. Cationic forms of amino acids can be considered to be the reactive species in acid medium. The attack of NBN on the α-carbon of zwitter-ionic form of amino acid is more feasible since it has relatively lower electron den-

sity than the anionic form¹⁹. The first order dependence on [substrate] and [oxidant] reveals that overall rate may involve the interaction of HOBr and amino acid in the rate determining step. But first order in the [substrate] and a definite intercept in the $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{sub}]$ plot, suggest that the decomposition of the complex formed from the substrate and HOBr is the rate determining step as shown in Scheme 2.

Here R = -C₃H₇ for Val, -C₄H₉ for Leu, Ile, PhCH₂- for Phe

Scheme 2

The rate law for the above mechanism may be divided as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate} &= \frac{-d[\text{NBN}]}{dT} \\ &= k_d[\text{Complex}] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{k_d k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{NBN}][\text{SH}^+]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{NA}][\text{H}^+]} \quad (9)$$

$$[\text{NBN}]_T = [\text{NBN}] + [\text{HOBr}] + [\text{Complex}] \quad (10)$$

$$= [\text{NBN}] + \frac{k_1 [\text{NBN}]}{k_{-1} [\text{NA}]} \quad (11)$$

$$+ \frac{[\text{NBN}]_T}{k_{-1} [\text{NA}] + k_1 + \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]}{k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{H}^+]}} = [\text{NBN}] \quad (12)$$

Substituting [NBN] in eq. (9)

$$\frac{-d[\text{NBN}]_T}{dT} = \frac{k_d k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{NBN}]_T [\text{SH}^+]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{NA}][\text{H}^+] + k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{H}^+] + k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{SH}^+]} \quad (13)$$

On rearranging the equation

$$\left[\frac{k_{-1} k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{NA}][\text{H}^+]}{k_d k_1 k_2 k_3} + \frac{k_{-2} k_{-3} [\text{H}^+]}{k_d k_2 k_3} \right] \frac{1}{[\text{SH}^+]} + \frac{1}{k_d} = \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} \quad 14$$

The rate-determining step proposed in the above mechanism predicts negligible salt effect which has been experimentally observed. In the proposed mechanism, the formation of aldimine (RCH=NH) from the hypobromite derivative takes place in a single step.

Since the separation of intermediate is not possible and hence the most plausible mechanism is given in the paper. The formation of the complex involves the charge separation which leads to a negative solvent effect. This has been confirmed by the increase in rate with decreasing dielectric constant of the medium. The involvement of amino acid molecule in the rate-determining step leads to different values of k_{obs} for different initial concentrations of amino acids under study, namely, valine, leucine, isoleucine and phenylalanine.

The proposed mechanism is well supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and thermodynamic parameters. The negative entropy of activation indicates the complex formation as suggested in the above reaction mechanism, and also indicates that the complex is more ordered than reactants²⁰. High positive values of the free energy of activation and the enthalpy of activa-

tion show that the transition state is highly solvated.

Experimental

The amino acids (A.R., Loba) were used as such. Standard solution of NBN (m.p. 210 °C) was prepared afresh in water and its purity was checked iodometrically. Hydrochloric acid (AnalaR) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Sodium perchlorate (Merck) was used to keep the ionic strength constant. Acetic acid (A.R., Qualigen) was purified by standard method²¹. Mercuric acetate was added to suppress the formation of free bromine which otherwise would have vitiated the results. Mercuric acetate did not interfere with the results²². Conductivity water was used throughout the study. Other chemicals used were of analytical grade. The reaction was carried out under pseudo-first order condition ($[amino\ acid] \gg [NBN]$). The reaction was followed potentiometrically by setting up a cell made up of the reaction mixture into which the platinum electrode and reference electrode (SCE) were dipped. The e.m.f of the cell was measured periodically using a Equip-Tronics (EQ-DGD) potentiometer. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed from the plots of $\log (E_t - E_\infty)$ against time were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$. The course of the reaction was studied for more than two half-lives.

Stoichiometry and product analysis :

A mixture of amino acid ($0.01\ mol\ dm^{-3}$), NBN ($0.05\ mol\ dm^{-3}$) and HCl ($0.8\ mol\ dm^{-3}$) was made upto 100 ml with water and acetic acid mixture (1 : 1). After the reaction was complete, the excess of NBN was determined iodometrically and several determinations with various amino acids indicated 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The overall stoichiometry of the oxidation reaction may be represented as

In a typical experiment, a mixture of amino acid (Val, Leu, Ile and Phe, $1\ mol\ dm^{-3}$) and NBN ($1.5\ g, 0.2\ mol\ dm^{-3}$) was made up to 50 ml with acetic acid-water mixture (1 : 1) in presence of HCl ($0.8\ mol\ dm^{-3}$). The mixture was allowed to stand for 12 h in the dark to ensure completion of the reaction. It was then treated with an excess (125 ml) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in HCl ($2\ mol\ dm^{-3}$) and set aside for 10 h. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, recrystallised from ethanol (80%). The product was found to be identical (m.p. and

m.m.p.) with an authentic sample of DNP of isobutyraldehyde, isovaleraldehyde, 2-methylbutyraldehyde and phenylacetaldehyde respectively²³. Carbon dioxide and ammonia were detected by baryta water and Nessler's reagent respectively. The presence of corresponding aldehyde and ammonium ions were also confirmed by the spot tests²⁴ with chromotropic acid and *p*-nitrobenzenediazonium chloride respectively.

Conclusion :

The rate of the reaction depends on the first power of concentration of H^+ and oxidant. Added nicotinamide retards the reaction. Addition of salts to the reaction medium has no effect on the rate. Increase in temperature increases the rate of reaction. The activation parameters are evaluated from the study of oxidation at different temperatures. The products obtained in each case (the corresponding aldehydes) were isolated and characterized.

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